

INSTRUCTIONAL INFORMATION

The following module template has been developed as part of Work Package 7 of the EU-funded GoGreen project. The module is designed in a skeletal format to allow for broad adaptation to a wide range of existing curricula and professional development schemes. To enhance flexibility, the module is divided into theme blocks with suggested content, assessments, and activities. The template has been constructed to serve as foundational material for curriculum development or course integration.

INTENDED AUDIENCE

This module may be adapted for the instruction of conservation and conservation science learners at the undergraduate, postgraduate, and professional level with a focus on metals and glass objects. The activities and assessments of this module are developed for a group audience.

MODULE DELIVERY

This module is best suited for in-person, practical instruction. Content in this module will be delivered using a case study. Throughout the module learners will:

- Conduct tests on their case study using various cleaning and stabilisation materials and methods
- Observe and record the effects of the different materials and methods
- Utilise analytical techniques and simple-assessment approaches to assess, compare, and evaluate the effectiveness of cleaning and stabilisation methods

PRE-REQUISITE KNOWLEDGE

Prior to the module, learners should be prepped with the following skills and knowledge which may be acquired from previous coursework or through complementary GoGreen modules:

1. Knowledge of the foundational principles for object conservation and the chemical and physical attributes associated with the deterioration of objects both from a material science perspective and a conservation perspective.
2. Awareness of policies, frameworks, and methodologies within the cultural heritage sector that may be applied to the remedial conservation of objects. Supported by the GoGreen module **Leadership in Green Conservation**
3. Knowledge of the GoGreen definition for green conservation and green parameters, and the Green Decision-Making Model (DMM). Supported by the GoGreen module **Leadership in Green Conservation**
4. Knowledge of the tools and frameworks used for understanding object stability and risks to make informed green decisions. Supported by the GoGreen module **Determining Material Sensitivities and Green Decision-Making**

MISSION STATEMENT

To empower students and professionals to make informed green(er) choices in their personal practice by integrating tools, metrics, and guidelines for selecting and evaluating materials and methods for the remedial conservation of objects.

DESCRIPTION

Green Treatment and Their Assessment: Objects explores the green frameworks, tools, and guidelines relevant for the selection and application of green(er) materials and methods for the conservation of objects. The content emphasises conservation methods for the cleaning of metals, and stabilisation of metal and glass objects developed within the GoGreen project and broader EU-funded Green Cluster. The content emphasises efficacy, safety, and ethical considerations of these materials and methods, and demonstrates how the frameworks and tools may be applied to other remedial conservation practices.

Content is delivered through practical, case study-based learning, supporting student-centred development of both theoretical and practical skills. Learners are encouraged to apply green thinking to their own conservation practice or a selected case study, reflecting on the practicalities, challenges, and limitations of sustainable approaches in real-world contexts.

LEARNING GOALS AND OUTCOMES

Main Goal Provide conservation researchers and conservators with the knowledge and practical tools needed for the development, assessment and use of green(er) approaches for the conservation of objects

Subsidiary Goals

- Develop an understanding of tools, metrics, and guidelines that inform green(er) decision-making for the conservation of objects
- Examine new materials and techniques used for the remedial conservation of objects and their comparative performance against commonly used materials in terms of the green parameters
- Evaluate the efficacy of cleaning and stabilisation practices utilising new techniques and technologies from the GoGreen project
- Develop practical knowledge of cleaning and stabilisation approaches through the application of assessment strategies and the green parameters.

By the end of this module,Learning Outcomes

1. **(Evaluation)** Evaluate the 'greenness' of materials used in the cleaning and stabilisation of objects by applying the *Green Parameters and Frameworks*: (1) Globally Harmonized System (GHS), (2) Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA), (3) Safe and Sustainable by Design principles, and (4) Guidelines.
2. **(Comparison)** Compare cleaning and stabilisation strategies used in the remedial conservation of objects, considering their impact through a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.
3. **(Assessment)** Gain knowledge of new analytical techniques and simple assessment approaches to assess treated surfaces to compare and evaluate different applications and materials for the cleaning and stabilisation of objects.
4. **(Reflection)** Demonstrate theoretical and practical competency in reflecting on the selection and application of green(er) cleaning and stabilisation methods for object conservation by discussing the processes, decisions, and outcomes involved in their application on a case study.

RECOMMEND READINGS

Visit the GoGreen Zenodo for the full module bibliography

Fife, G. R. (Ed.). (2021). *Green(er) solvents in conservation: an introductory guide*. Archetype Publications.

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Glass

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Metal

Passaretti, A., & Russo, S. (2020). Innovative Approaches towards a Green and Sustainable Metal Conservation: Highlights of Analytical Sciences in Switzerland. *CHIMIA*, 74(7–8), 611. <https://doi.org/10.2533/chimia.2020.611>

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- Silva, M., Rosado, T., Lopes Da Silva, Z., Nóbrega, Y., Silveira, D., Candeias, A., & Caldeira, A. T.** (2020). Green Bioactive Compounds: Mitigation Strategies for Cultural Heritage. *Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage*, 133-142 Pages. <https://doi.org/10.6092/ISSN.1973-9494/10347>
- Passaretti, A., Cuvillier, L., Guilminot, E., Sciutto, G., & Joseph, E.** (2023). Biocleaning of historical metal artworks: Innovative green gels amended with microbial derivatives. *Frontiers in Materials*, 10, 1277972. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2023.1277972>
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- Wu, Q., & Joseph, E.** (2025). The application of an innovative green material 'sapoline' for the cleaning of historical metal objects. *ICOM-CC Meta I2025*, Cardiff, 01-05 September 2025.
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Wu, Q., Zhou, H., Bertrand, L., Stols-Witlox, M., Brambilla, L., & Joseph, E. (2025). Natural and Artificial Aging Methods for Silver Mock-ups in Recent Conservation and Heritage Studies: A Short Review. *Chemistry-Methods*, 5(5), e202400055. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cmttd.202400055>.

SUPPLEMENTARY READINGS

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GREEN TREATMENTS AND THEIR ASSESSMENT: OBJECTS				
THEME	TOPICS	DESCRIPTION	LEARNING OUTCOMES	ACTIVITIES + ASSESSMENTS
Foundation and Tools for the Green Conservation of Objects	<i>Green Frameworks and Tools for Sustainable Decision-Making</i>	Introduces green conservation, the green frameworks, and practical tools for sustainable decision-making in object conservation.	Evaluate the 'greenness' of materials used in the cleaning and stabilisation of objects by applying the Green Parameters and Frameworks: (1) Globally Harmonized System (GHS), (2) Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA), (3) Safe and Sustainable by Design principles, and (4) Guidelines.	<p>Activity/Assessment: Using relevant green frameworks and tools, evaluate the 'greenness' of a conservation material commonly used within personal context and present findings.</p> <p>Activity/Assessment: Choose and use a tool for green(er) decision-making on a provided case study for the remedial conservation of objects. Consider the appropriateness of the treatment using a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.</p>
	<i>Materials and Methods for Cleaning and Stabilisation</i>	Explores green(er) advancements in the materials and methods for cleaning and stabilising metals, and how they compare to traditional approaches. Materials and methods from within the Green Cluster are discussed in more detail to provide a basis for practical application.	Compare cleaning and stabilisation strategies used in the remedial conservation of objects, considering their impact through a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.	<p>Activity: Investigate 1-2 newly identified materials and methods for the cleaning and stabilisation of metals and create a properties profile that includes the physical properties, toxicity and hazard metrics, and LCA impacts. Exchange with fellow students to identify how chosen materials and methods compare.</p> <p>Activity: Apply a chosen material or method identified in previous activity on a case study. Exchange with fellow students and identify how materials and methods compare against commonly used approaches. Consider effective communication strategies for presenting the full profile to broader class, for example such as star diagrams.</p>
<i>Practical Application of Cleaning and Stabilisation Materials and Methods</i>	Practical focused on the application of new materials and methods highlighted in the Green Cluster and on-going innovations for the remedial conservation of metals. Utilises suggested module delivery for instruction.			
Green Treatments for Metals	<i>Materials and Methods for Stabilisation</i>	Explores green(er) advancements in the materials and methods for the stabilisation of glass and how they compare to traditional approaches. Materials and methods from within the Green Cluster are discussed in more detail to provide a basis for practical application.	Compare cleaning and stabilisation strategies used in the remedial conservation of objects, considering their impact through a holistic approach aligned with the green parameters.	<p>Activity: Investigate 1-2 newly identified materials and methods for the stabilisation of glass objects and create a properties profile that include the physical properties, toxicity and hazard metrics, and LCA impacts. Exchange with fellow students to identify how chosen materials and methods compare.</p> <p>Activity: Apply a chosen material or method identified in previous activity on a case study. Exchange with fellow students and identify how materials and methods compare against commonly used approaches. Consider effective communication strategies for presenting the full profile to broader class, for example such as star diagrams.</p> <p>Activity: Explore when and how new analytical techniques can be applied using green parameters and assess their added value in treatment or research. Reflect on how these techniques and methods can become part of your own conservation toolbox.</p>
	<i>Practical Application of Stabilisation Materials and Methods for Glass</i>	Practical session focused on the application of new materials and methods highlighted in the Green Cluster and on-going innovations for the remedial conservation of glass objects. Utilises suggested module delivery for instruction.		
	<i>Practical Application of Assessment Techniques</i>	Practical session focused on the application of assessment techniques highlighted in the Green Cluster and on-going research. Utilises suggested module delivery for instruction.		

GREEN TREATMENTS AND THEIR ASSESSMENT: OBJECTS				
THEME	TOPICS	DESCRIPTION	LEARNING OUTCOMES	ACTIVITIES + ASSESSMENTS
Testing and Monitoring of Treated Surfaces	<i>Introduction to Assessment Techniques for the Evaluation of Cleaning and Stabilisation Strategies</i>	Introduces new analytical techniques and simple assessment methods developed for the evaluation of cleaning and stabilisation methods.	Gain knowledge of new analytical techniques and simple assessment approaches to assess treated surfaces to compare and evaluate different applications and materials for the cleaning and stabilisation of objects.	<p>Activity/Assessment: Present on a specific key risk, benefit, or limitation of 1 to 2 analytical techniques or simple assessment methods.</p> <p>Activity: Explore when and how new analytical techniques can be applied using green parameters and assess their added value in treatment or research. Reflect on how these techniques and methods can become part of your own conservation toolbox.</p>
	<i>Practical Application of Assessment Techniques</i>	Practical session focused on the application of assessment techniques highlighted in the Green Cluster and on-going research. Utilises suggested module delivery for instruction.		<p>Activity: Apply available monitoring and assessment techniques onto case studies to evaluate the efficacy of materials and methods. Expand the properties profile created in earlier activities to include the efficacy of the materials and application methods.</p> <p>Assessment: Present full properties profile using visual communications strategies.</p>
Conservation Practice	<i>Putting into Practice</i>	Provides learners with the opportunity to apply new knowledge to personal context by integrating green(er) thinking into existing conservation practice or on a case study and assessing the practicalities and limitations.	Demonstrate theoretical and practical competency in reflecting on the selection and application of green(er) cleaning and stabilisation methods for object conservation by discussing the processes, decisions, and outcomes involved in their application on a case study.	<p>Activity/Assessment: Present on a case study identifying strategies for integrating green(er) strategies in one's professional practice. Analyse the practicality and limitations of suggested strategies in real world contexts.</p> <p>Activity/Assessment: Create a mood board for a personal mission statement.</p> <p>Activity: Group discussion How can different stakeholders contribute to greener decision-making within the complexities of cultural heritage conservation?</p>

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

AUTHORS AND CONTRIBUTORS

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